

Paper for Reading Report

English Class

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Vocational School : School English Analysis (IKN-Sains)

Object:

Braydon Young Paper Analysis for ***THE PORTRAYAL OF AMERICAN CULTURE AND SUICIDE IN THE SONG “1-800-273-8255” SUNG BY LOGIC (FT. ALESSIA CARA & KHALID)***

Background and Analysis

This paper will analyze a song entitled 1-800-273-8255 sung by Logic, ft. Alessia Cara and Khalid. This analysis will focus on the meaning of the song lyrics that relate to the issue of suicide and also the purpose of the text features and context in the song. This song is a literary work that contains unwanted events. This song tells about the way people in the United States and even the world, face and respond to the problems they have in ways other than suicide (Niederkrötenhaler & Draper, 2021). Therefore, we can discuss other options that the community can use. The reason for choosing this song is because it illustrates the importance of the issue globally and aims to warn the issue.

The message of the song is very clear. Until now artists, including artists and singers or people who can influence others, have direct sympathy and empathy for those who think their lives are not worth living. At first, logic does this by realistically depicting the person's character as his own, and therefore through this, it is seen that most artists represent their emotions through the art they produce and true meanings can be obtained with logical thinking. This song is dedicated to telling people suffering from depression that taking drastic action against this negativity is not the answer. The experience of depression is not permanent but when one does experience it, one has to try harder to truly acknowledge the gift of love to convince oneself that the pain will never end.

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Article/Media/Literacy Resources based Questions:

1) Is it Available data or information to answer it?

Yes, the quantitative part of my research is based on real data which, in this case, are numbers showing suicide rates and it is later on being interpreted by qualitative research.

2) Is the data or information obtained through scientific methods, such as interviews, observations, questionnaires, documentation, participation, and evaluations/tests,

In some parts of the research paper, the quantitative part of the content are obtained from secondary sources from online websites, journals and interviews that are done by other people while the qualitative part of the research is done by observing several factors to find out hidden meanings of the song itself based on the result of the qualitative research.

3) Does it meet the originality requirements, identified through previous research mapping (state of the arts)?

Since what we are doing is based on my own skills and abilities, we did this research paper without being corrected by other people. Only data in the form of numbers as proof that the research paper shows awareness of suicide as a global issue are taken from online sources but these numbers are being explained in detail in my research paper by my own ideas. Not only that, plagiarism is also being avoided. Hence, I think that yes, my paper does meet the originality requirements.

4) Does it make a significant theoretical contribution to the development of science?

Yes, I believe that my research in spreading the awareness of suicide will help contribute to the development of science, especially in the advancement in medicine and the cure to mental illnesses.

5) Does it regard controversial and unique issues that are currently happening?

Yes, since my research is about a global issue that is happening all around the world, it needs to be taken action in order to help raise the awareness.

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6) The problem requires an answer and an immediate solution, but the answer is not yet known to the general public.

Therefore, public action needs to contribute to the aim of the research paper so that it could be accomplished.

7) The problem is posed within the limits of the researcher's interest (field of study) and ability.

Yes, the problem is posed within the limits of the researcher's interest since this research is done by analyzing the style of the songwriter's way of creating this song to spread awareness of suicide.

8) What developments or shifts were taking place at the time the event occurred?

I am hoping that the advancement in technologies will take place in order to help suicidal people or even victims of mental illnesses since the problem is getting more and more significant.

9) What are the benefits of this research for the development of science and society at large in the future?

People experiencing depression will receive enough help to prevent them from suicide in the future.

Bibliography and Recommended Papers

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